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**SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL INTERPRETATION OF TODAY'S WORLD
GEOECONOMIC AND GEOPOLITICAL LANDSCAPE** <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14325895>**ABSTRACT**

While the current global economic and political processes are rapidly developing and the struggles of the countries of the world in the world political arena are intensifying, their geo-economic and geo-political landscape is related to a number of economic and political factors. This article explores the interconnectedness between geo-economics and geopolitics, two fields that play a crucial role in shaping global affairs. By examining the relationship between economic factors and political power, this study aims to shed light on how nations strategically utilize their resources to gain geopolitical advantages. The article employs a multidisciplinary approach, drawing on various methods and a comprehensive literature review to provide a holistic understanding of this complex interplay. The findings emphasize the significance of considering both economic and political dimensions when analyzing global dynamics.

Key words: geo-economics, geopolitics, geo-economic policy, geopolitical landscape, political consensus, transnational economy, business system.

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**BUGUNGI DUNYO GEOIQTISODIY VA GEOSIYOSIY MANZARASINING IJTIMOIIY-
FALSAFIY TALQINI****ANNOTATSIYA**

Hozirgi global iqtisodiy va siyosiy jarayonlar jadal rivojlanib, jahon siyosiy maydonida dunyo davlatlarining kurashlari kuchayib borayotgan bir paytda ularning geoiqtisodiy va geosiyosiy manzarasi bir qator iqtisodiy va siyosiy omillar bilan bog'liq bo'lmoqda. Ushbu maqolada geoiqtisodiyot va geosiyosat o'rtasidagi o'zaro bog'liqlikni, global munosabatlarni shakllantirishda hal qiluvchi rol o'ynaydigan ikki sohaning ijtimoiy-falsafiy jihatdan tahlil qilib berilgan. Shuningdek,

iqtisodiy omillar va siyosiy kuchlar o'rtasidagi munosabatlarni mustahkamlash va geosiyosiy afzalliklarga erishish uchun davlatlar o'z resurslaridan strategik maqsadlarda foydalanishini yoritib berilgan. Maqolada ushbu murakkab o'zaro ta'sirni yaxlit tushunish uchun turli usullar va keng qamrovli adabiyotlarni ko'rib chiqishga asoslangan ko'p tarmoqli yondashuv qo'llaniladi. Natijalar global dinamikani tahlil qilishda ham iqtisodiy, ham siyosiy jihatlarni hisobga olish muhimligini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: geoiqtisodiyot, geosiyosat, geoiqtisodiy siyosat, geosiyosiy landshaft, siyosiy konsensus, transmilliy iqtisodiyot, biznes tizimi.

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СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКАЯ ИНТЕРПРЕТАЦИЯ ГЕОЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО И ГЕОПОЛИТИЧЕСКОГО КАРТИНЫ СОВРЕМЕННОГО МИРА

АННОТАЦИЯ

В настоящее время современные глобальные экономические и политические процессы стремительно развиваются и обостряется борьба стран мира на мировой политической арене, их геоэкономический и геополитический ландшафт связан с рядом экономических и политических факторов. В данной статье с социально-философской точки зрения анализируется взаимосвязь геоэкономики и геополитики - двух областей, играющих решающую роль в формировании глобальных отношений. Также подчеркивается, что государства используют свои ресурсы в стратегических целях для укрепления отношений между экономическими факторами и политическими силами и достижения геополитических преимуществ. В статье используется междисциплинарный подход, основанный на различных методах и всестороннем обзоре литературы, чтобы целостно понять это сложное взаимодействие. Результаты показывают важность рассмотрения как экономических, так и политических аспектов при анализе глобальной динамики.

Ключевые слова: геоэкономика, геополитика, геоэкономическая политика, геополитический ландшафт, политический консенсус, транснациональная экономика, бизнес-система.

Introduction: Geoeconomics and geopolitics are two closely intertwined disciplines that offer valuable insights into the complex dynamics of international relations. While geopolitics primarily focuses on the strategic influence of geography on politics, geoeconomics examines the interplay between economic factors and political power. This article aims to explore the relationship between these two fields and highlight their importance in understanding contemporary global affairs.

The geo-economic landscape of the world that is forming and developing today has a complex and conflicting structure, which mainly includes the following socio-economic processes: firstly, the spaces occupied by the national economy, which are interacting, connecting and cooperating in the world economy, and the geographical territories of any country occupied by the transnational economy image; secondly, to interpret the global space in a form that is convenient for carrying out strategic operations and making strategic decisions; thirdly, to divide the global economic space into separate socio-economic areas, that is, to divide into regions; fourthly, the area aimed at collecting its share of world income spaces. Therefore, earning and profiting in a new way in the world economy is one of the main attributes of the geo-economic approach to the implementation of operations the geo-economic landscape of today's world a phenomenon that synthesizes the multi-faceted economic activity of multi-level, highly mobile inter-firm and inter-state systems. Achieving success through this phenomenon is determined, firstly, by the ability to quickly adapt to its demands and changes

and integrate into them, and secondly, by having advanced intellectual, informational, and communication capabilities.

For us, knowing the structural structure of this landscape and timely mastering the status and requirements of their mechanisms of action gives us the opportunity to carry out strategic operations in the geo-economic space for better income and profit.

One of the parts of the geo-economic and geo-political landscape of today's world is the political-administrative structure of the states.

The political-administrative structure of states is a political-legal mechanism consisting of their state structure and forms of government, territorial, political, and administrative units, their borders, political, strategic, and administrative centers, as well as international, state, and local communications. Currently, there are about 230 countries with different political and administrative structures in the world, 194 of which are members of the UN.

For example, if we analyze the political-administrative structure of 48 countries located on the Asian continent:

- 17 of them are presidential parliamentary republics;
- 10 are constitutional monarchies;
- 1 is a presidential republic (the Republic of Iraq Al-Jumhuriya al-Iraqiya);
- 2 are a federation of emirates (the United Arab Emirates, Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan);
- 1 presidential parliamentary socialist republic (Socialist Republic of Vietnam), 6 presidential republics;
- 2 socialist republics (Democratic People's Republic of Korea, People's Republic of China);
- 1 people's democratic republic (Laos People's Democratic Republic);
- 1 is a republic (Union of Myanmar Burma);
- 1 is an absolute theocratic monarchy (Kingdom of Saudi Arabia);
- 2 is an absolute monarchy (State of Qatar, Sultanate of Oman);
- 1 is a theocratic presidential republic (Islamic Republic of Iran);
- 1 is a presidential parliamentary federal republic (Republic of India);
- 1 parliamentary federal republic (Islamic Republic of Pakistan);
- 1 state bodies and political parties of East Timor are in the process of formation [1, 27-p].

It can be seen from these data that the political-administrative structure of the states is reflected in the political map of the world in the form of the state-administrative border of the world structure, and its dialectical content and essence can be seen from the point of view of geo-economic policy: first, different countries with different political structures and legal status that the broad panorama of strategic alliances and integrated associations united for different political goals is reflected as a union of one or another state, secondly, that the national economy is divided into various socio-economic systems within the predetermined state-administrative borders; thirdly, we see that the political behavior of states is organized, which consists of a bold desire to dominate culturally-educationally, religiously-morally, ethnically.

From the point of view of geopolitics, the political map of the world is the wheel axles and centers of influence of political forces at different levels in the world, firstly, to ensure superiority over other peoples, nations, and peoples by solving them by military means; and secondly, which is a unique historical field of political games that have caused not only regional majors but also bloody wars on a global scale several times in the history of mankind.

Geopolitics is not yet out of the picture. It sharpens the methods of waging "hot and cold wars" of local and global importance on the political map of the world and polishes them. On the basis of this, political forces with great economic power use their authority and influence not only through diplomatic means but also through military means and strategic political tricks to rule over other people, nations, people's specific life spaces, and their state administration. It is not difficult to understand that the issue of acquiring new colonial economic spaces by removing the borders from the borders of world countries lies. In order to achieve this, political-ideological means are being used; that is, in the geopolitical memory of the people, they are trying to revive the ghosts of the eras and times that have already fallen from the stage of history, and in the consciousness of the present

and future generations, they are trying to form an age-old geopolitical mentality of thinking that does not correspond to a specific situation. The main goal of this is to stop the blood feuds, the psychosis of sovereignty, political revenge, and revenge that happened between nations and peoples, to incite them against each other, to ignite the spark, and to repeatedly group together enemies, friends, allies, and partners. Based on the invasion idea of “divide and rule,” it is to acquire new areas of vital need.

Thus, the role of the political-administrative structure of the countries of the world in the geo-economic landscape of today’s world is: firstly, the sovereignty, form of government, and state-administrative borders of the developed countries at different levels; secondly, for what purposes they became members of international political organizations; thirdly, what kind of political and legal status the administrative units within the state have; fourthly, it is to show the level of political consensus reached by subjects entering into political dialogue by knowing how committed they are to universal and national political values, etc.

Materials and methods: To comprehensively analyze the relationship between geoeconomics and geopolitics, this study employs a multidisciplinary approach. It combines elements of political science, economics, geography, and international relations. The research draws on qualitative methods such as literature reviews, case studies, and theoretical analysis to provide a nuanced understanding of the subject matter.

One of the main components of the emerging geo-economic landscape of the world today is the organizational and economic structure of the world economy. Today, the information presented in the books of O.V. Kornienko [2], A.P. Kuzyakin and M.A. Semichev [3], O. Akhmedov and Abdurakhmanov [4] can be classified as follows based on logical generalization:

1. “Big Eight”: USA, Japan, Canada, Germany, France, Great Britain, Italy, and Russia.
2. Developed countries: Australia, New Zealand, South Africa, Israel, Brazil, and others
3. Countries transitioning to a market economy—Russia and other CIS countries, Eastern European countries, etc.
4. Backward countries: countries of the Middle East, tropical African countries
5. “New industrial countries”: Malaysia, Thailand, Indonesia, the Philippines, Turkey, Chile, and others.
6. Countries that make a good living by selling their natural resources are Iran, Iraq, Venezuela, Kuwait, Saudi Arabia, Qatar, Libya, the UAE, Algeria, Nigeria, Ecuador, Gabon, Indonesia, and Brunei.
7. Countries with high recreational opportunities are Monaco, Cyprus, Switzerland, and a number of countries in the Caribbean.
8. Countries with a dualistic economy are Mexico, India, Oman, and Bahrain.
9. The smallest European countries are Andorra, Monaco, Liechtenstein, and San Marino.
10. East Asian “tigers” or “4 dragons”: South Korea, Singapore, Taiwan, and Hong Kong.

The role of this classification in the geo-economic landscape of today’s world is, firstly, based on the economic indicators of the countries in production and trade, showing their place in the world economic system; secondly, what kind of geo-economic policy they are trying to create new geo-economic spaces to satisfy their needs and interests; and thirdly, it is expressed by reflecting how they earn and benefit from the realization of their natural resources in new geo-economic spaces by combining them with new technologies on the basis of national economic values.

Results: While doing this research, some books and dissertations were analyzed. The main results were drawn after reviewing these resources.

We can see that, as a result of the impact of globalization, the geo-economic landscape of today’s world began to acquire a more colorful picture with the emergence of the entrepreneurial system of economic activity typical of the modern market economy in the organizational and economic structure of the world economy.

“The entrepreneurial system is a set of economic relations and legal-organizational aspects of entrepreneurship characteristic of entrepreneurship, i.e., a set of related policies” [4, 55], which includes its object, subject, laws, ethical and moral standards, policy-making style, and infrastructure.

Entrepreneurship as a socio-economic activity is owned by private individuals, corporations, collective-group cooperatives, associations, companies, and the state; open, i.e., permitted; and covert, i.e., confidential, depending on the legality; depending on the direction, industrial, agricultural, or service; it is divided into small, medium, and large enterprises depending on their scale [5, 58]. Business activity is carried out within the firm. Accordingly, companies conduct economic activity in private, partnership, limited liability, and unlimited liability forms. Firms join for some purpose in economic activity. As a result, a number of associations of firms are formed. Groups of businesspersons conducting geopolitics in the geo-economic space for a strategic purpose unite into holding companies, conglomerates, and cartels. Because of the international merger of companies, new entities—transnational TNCs and international companies (IFCs)—appeared in the international economic arena.

Discussion: The interplay between geoeconomics and geopolitics is evident in various aspects of global affairs. Economically powerful nations often leverage their resources and economic influence to gain geopolitical advantages. For instance, control over vital natural resources can enhance a nation's political leverage on the global stage. Similarly, economic sanctions can be used as a geopolitical tool to exert pressure on rival nations.

Furthermore, geoeconomics plays a crucial role in shaping regional alliances and conflicts. Economic cooperation and trade agreements can foster diplomatic ties and promote stability, while economic disparities can lead to tensions and conflicts. Understanding the economic dimensions of geopolitical strategies is essential for formulating effective foreign policies and predicting potential conflicts.

If we look at the organizational economic activity of TNC with a philosophical eye, we can see that in their geo-economic space: first, the mother who makes strategic decisions; secondly, a daughter who is subordinate to the parent companies because of their participation in the system; thirdly, a branch operating elsewhere as a wholly owned subsidiary of the parent company; fourthly, we see that a clear hierarchy has emerged, which includes joint-stock companies that are subordinate to TNC based on their share of actives.

In the past 20 years of the 21st century, the number of TNCs has reached 90,000, with 850,000 branches. The number of employees in them is 72 million. Per person, they produce more than 2 trillion dollars. More than 150 million employees work in allied enterprises related to TNC. [6, 103-109]

Analyzing the activities of TNCs philosophically, their goal of integrating and connecting corporations and firms in geo-economic spaces is:

1. To strengthen their influence in existing markets
2. Increasing the efficiency of work there based on the pooling of resources;
3. Sales of new goods occupying markets;
4. Optimization of company management;
5. Implementation of diversification works;
6. It consists of fighting together against opponents and others.

The above philosophical analyses show that in the future, a new generation of producers based on new technologies and traders relying on the rapid flow of information will appear in the external economic structure of the world economy, enriching the geo-economic landscape of today's world and enjoying its "mirror", will continue to implement their geo-economic policy.

One of the next components of the emerging geo-economic and geo-political landscape of today's world is the types of economic activities in the world economy system and geo-economic regionalism.

Today, as the trend of specialization of economic activities in the world economic system increases, the processes of dividing existing geo-economic spaces into geo-economic regions producing certain types of goods are also accelerating. In the current conditions, geo-economic regions are considered one of the main driving forces of the world economic system, connecting it with other geo-economic areas. In this case, the concept of "region" is the world of individual people who have their own philosophical mentality, way of thinking, traditions, worldview, perception of

the world, people, nation, a special place where people lived, which has its place in historical space and time, geopolitical, various political forces and movements, “strong” and “weak” centers emerge from the shell of their location in specific spaces and gain more economic content.

In terms of economic activity, each geo-economic region has its own needs and interests. They can be divided into objective and subjective needs and interests. The objective needs and interests of the geo-economic region are determined by:

1. Geographical location of the region, transport, raw materials, weather conditions, etc.
2. Availability or absence of labor force and economic resources;
3. Level of socio-economic development;
4. Conditions were created to ensure economic security for sustainable development.

The subjective needs and interests of the geo-economic region are characterized by the valuable approach of the local elite and the historical and cultural traditions of regional community associations. Thus, a geo-economic region is an independent economic activity in the geo-economic space and is specialized in the production of certain types of products.

Conclusion: In this regard, it is possible to come to the following conclusions: First of all, the processes of dividing the geo-economic space into regions, i.e., the processes of dividing the geo-economic space into regions aimed at the production of certain types of goods, are gradually finding their reflection.

Secondly, the proportionality of activities in the world economic system and the mosaic of global specialized regions are clearly visible as factors in the systematic organization of the geo-economy.

Thirdly, the increasing specialization of types of economic activity and the strengthening of geo-economic regionalism, i.e., firstly, the growing transnational space, the world of international non-governmental organizations and financial and banking networks; secondly, the surreptitious globalization that is taking shape, the transnational world that is being “thrown away” in parallel with it; thirdly, the regions and man-made zones that make up the global infrastructure for the production of high-tech products; fourthly, it means that huge regions in the world are becoming specialized in the cultivation of resources and raw materials. Philosophically speaking, these are the economic lifeblood that keeps the emerging geo-economic landscape of the world alive, not dead.

It is difficult to imagine the emerging geo-economic landscape of today’s world without geo-financial processes. The geofinancial processes taking place in the field of economic activity today are the main factor in shaping the geoeconomic landscape of the world and determining its directions. The financial and currency systems of the state play a major role in geofinancial processes. In general, the exchange of currencies between countries is a complex socio-economic process that continues unceasingly, and the following factors influence its changes:

1. Changes in consumer tastes, that is, if consumer demand for products produced by a country increases, the currency rate of that country will also increase;
2. The relative change of income, i.e., the increase in national income leads to a decrease in the national currency rate;
3. The relative change of the price value, the increase of the price within the country, leads to the depreciation of the national currency;
4. Relativity of interest rates: reduction of interest rates on deposits leads to depreciation of the national currency;
5. An increase in customs duties leads to an increase in the national currency rate. Expectation of an increase in the exchange rate.
6. An increase in the euro rate leads to a decrease in the dollar rate.
7. Organizes speculative actions in currency markets.

The financial and currency systems of each country consist of financial objects, subjects, financial relations, financial mechanisms, financial policies, and financial institutions and operate at the levels of microfinance, macrofinance, and meta finance. In this, the role of the financial market stands out. It consists of stock and money markets. Its money market consists of credit and currency

markets. In the credit market, money is sold in order to use it, and in the foreign exchange market, various national currencies are traded [5, 111-123].

Today, the world's largest credit and currency organizations include: the International Monetary Fund, established in 1944 with 184 member countries; the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development, established in 1990 with 60 member countries; the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development, established in 1994 with 184 member countries; the International Center for Settlement of Investment Disputes, established in 1966 with 166 member countries; the Multilateral Investment Guarantee Agency, established in 1988 with 166 member countries; the Asian Development Bank, established in 1965 with 47 member countries; and others. These organizations are one of the important factors in determining the future directions of the geo-economic landscape of today's world [7, 85].

One of the important links in the geo-economic landscape of today's world is the market price system of goods produced in the world economy. It is known from economics that the price is the amount of money paid to buy a unit of goods and services in the market [5, 45-56]. It is wholesale and retail, depending on the fields of application; depending on the scope of implementation, local-regional, national, and international; depending on its level, it performs the functions of measurement, stimulation, regulation, and competition tool, divided into absolute and relative prices. Therefore, this process cannot be avoided in the philosophical research of the formation and development of the geo-economic landscape of today's world. From the point of view of the dialectic of economic development, today the vital need in the world is to divide spaces into geo-economically new systems on the basis of inter-firm, international, general, private, individual, and technological forms of division of labor. The new geo-economic entities that are their derivatives are concerns, consortia, transnational corporations, international combines, production-commercial associations, firms, and other similar complexes that participate in the implementation of national and internationalized import-export operations in world markets. As a result, the world market is forced to operate in a complex, "multi-layered" version. Therefore, in each floor of the world market, from the upper floor of long-term commodity circulation aimed at "squeezing" strategic profits to the lower daily traditional market floor, there is a unique conjuncture of the market where goods are sold in what quantity, at what price, and at what price. is being sold at high speed [5, 56].

So, each floor has its own structure and methods of operation, which have a positive or negative effect on the pricing of goods. From the point of view of the geo-economic approach to this issue, which provides geo-economic policy, it is possible to perceive the world market as a dialectically interconnected dynamic system of selected commodity markets. This system is being complemented by markets such as credit, currency, real estate, and the labor force. As a result, it is taking the form of a whole chain, and individual markets are forming its nations. On the basis of several separate special markets in this chain, the main markets are also emerging.

From the opinions expressed about the structural structure of the geo-economic and geo-political landscape of today's world and their philosophical interpretations, it can be concluded that this landscape: firstly, the economic and political world that exists today and the objective and subjective factors that influence it are the impetus for the movement of influence and counter-influence on each other the reasons for their development, i.e., the source, expressing the internal relationships that will occur; secondly, the unique mechanism of their development, expressing the interconnections between the quantitative and qualitative changes taking place in the blood vessels of the economy, the production of goods, the financial market, money circulation, currency exchange, competition, entrepreneurship, etc.; and thirdly, it shows the direction of development in the world of economy, representing the connections between the new geo-economic landscape and the old economic landscape and the nature of their succession, the progress of the development of things and events in the aspects of socio-economic life, from the bottom up. Therefore, knowledge of the geo-economic and geo-political landscape of today's world is necessary for our independent country and for the class of middle owners' small businesses and private entrepreneurs who are being given a wide path for free economic and political activity. That is its methodological importance for the socio-economic sciences.

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